

SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON PROMOTING PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS IN FERGANA REGION

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Annotation: In this article, the reforms carried out in the field of physical education and popularization of sports in 2022-2026 are revealed on the example of Fergana region. Also, in the coverage of changes made in the sports system in recent years were also described.

Key words and phrases: physical education, popularization of sports, patriotism, youth, five initiatives, Development strategy, healthy lifestyle.

Аннотация: В данной статье на примере Ферганской области раскрываются реформы, проводимые в сфере физического воспитания и популяризации спорта в 2022-2026 годах. Также в освещении статьи были описаны изменения, произошедшие в спортивной системе за последние годы.

Ключевые слова и фразы: физическое воспитание, популяризация спорта, патриотизм, молодежь, пять инициатив, стратегия развития, здоровый образ жизни.

INTRODUCTION. Popularization of physical education and sports in Uzbekistan is defined as one of the important directions of social policy. Because sport serves to strengthen the health of the population, to educate the young generation to be healthy and well-rounded, to establish a healthy lifestyle in the society. Prevents various diseases and harmful habits among young people. Sport plays an important role in the formation of high culture and patriotism. Achievements in this field will make the country known to the world and will give pride to all compatriots.

Extensive work has been done in this regard in Uzbekistan. Necessary conditions have been created for the population, especially the young generation, to regularly engage in physical education and mass sports. Modern sports complexes were built in cities and villages. "Five Initiatives" competitions have become a means of introducing young people to mass sports and a healthy lifestyle. A continuous system for selecting talented children and training professional athletes has been created. Boys and girls who have demonstrated their abilities during training in general education schools and children's sports complexes are taken to children's and teenagers' sports schools and sports colleges and are educated based on professional

approaches. He is improving his skills in higher educational institutions and training sessions.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS. The topic under study was not a special complex research object, but it has its own historiography. In the article, the historiography of the subject studied during the implementation of the systematic direction was analyzed based on the norms of its methodological and ideological generality, as well as from the point of view of historicity. For example, in the works created by researchers N.V.Zisman, Y.S.Sholomitsky, Y.A.Kova-lev, the formation and development of the culture of physical education in Uzbekistan, some considerations regarding some aspects of this problem are expressed. Also, in the researches of L.R. Ayrapetyans, T.S. Usman-Khojayevev, E.A. Koshbakhtiyev, F.A. Kerimov, R.S. Salomov, the problems of physical culture and sports, and the scientific and theoretical study of ways to strengthen the health of schoolchildren are covered [1].

METHODOLOGY. It is known that in research on the popularization of physical education and sports, it is possible to study and analyze the following areas: physical education, sports training and rehabilitation practice, history of physical education, sports medicine, world and O' history of the peoples of Uzbekistan, psychology (sports psychology), tourism [2]. Popularization of physical education and sports is related to human activity, production processes and various fields. In the studies conducted in the above areas, it was shown that the popularization of physical education and sports is an important area in the development of society, its development and problems. It is appropriate to briefly explain only some of their aspects that caused or contributed to the development of the science of physical education.

RESULTS. In the conditions of increasing global competition in all aspects of development, every country in the world needs to improve the quality of human capital. This requires a fundamental revision of approaches to the issues of permanent care for the health of the nation - a healthy outlook, physical, spiritual and intellectual health of the population of all ages, strengthening of physical health. Achieving a high level of physical education and the quality of life of the population in the Republic of Uzbekistan is an important condition for the implementation of the strategic task of sustainable development of the country. Within the framework of the implementation of the "Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan" of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, increasing the number of citizens who regularly engage in physical education and sports, developing the Olympic and Paralympic movement, all strata of the country's population throughout their lives providing the necessary conditions for regular physical education and sports will be one of the main factors for solving this task. These ideas are reflected in the 67th and 68th goals of the Development Strategy [3]. At the meeting of video selectors held on

March 19, 2019 under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev, it was decided to further strengthen the attention to our youth, to involve them widely in culture, art, physical education and sports, to inform the youth the issues of forming the skills of using technologies, promoting reading among the youth of our country, increasing the employment of women were emphasized, and work in the social, spiritual and educational spheres was launched on the basis of a new system 5 important initiatives were put forward.

In particular, within the implementation of five important initiatives, every year in the Fergana region, a public walk under the slogan "5000 steps for a healthy life", physical education classes, yoga classes for the health of enlightened patriarchs in the neighborhoods, "Workout" - neighborhood (street) fitness classes and chess competition, swimming competition among boys and girls living in the neighborhood in swimming pools, sports training to strengthen healthy lifestyle among unorganized women and 18 - "Mayor's Cup" football competitions were held among neighborhood youth aged 30 years.

In order to effectively implement the medium and long-term strategic tasks facing society, all efforts and resources should be directed to the promotion of a healthy lifestyle throughout the life of a person and the benefits of continuous participation in physical education and mass sports. It is necessary to ensure the involvement of all state institutions, non-state institutions and economic entities in this process. Currently, a number of good works are being carried out in all regions of the country in order to create conditions for the mass participation of the population in sports.

DISCUSSION. The healthy development of the population in the daily lifestyle is carried out in the following forms in order to ensure a wide range of movement activities.

1. Morning exercise
2. Training sessions on physical training
3. Public sports activities
4. Independent preparation

It is widely promoted in the country that every person engaged in physical education and sports should undergo a comprehensive medical examination regularly (once a year). He should also meet with his attending physician as needed. In addition, he should be able to independently control his health condition, physical development and level of physical fitness [4]. In the process of popularizing sports in the republic, proper nutrition and playing some kind of sport are widely promoted. It is necessary to record information about sleep, appetite, general condition, desire to engage in physical training in a self-monitoring diary every day. Load indicators and the body's reaction to exercise during training (for example, physical education - 12

minutes; water treatments, running 5 kilometers in 35 minutes; heart rate before and after running; heart rate after 3 minutes of running The need to take into account heart rate recovery index) is explained by athletes among the population. For this, in the self-monitoring diary, the number of times during the week morning gymnastics, water treatments, moderate walking or running, and their average duration, how many times a walk before sleep, wellness the number of trainings participated in the group and others are recorded.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, it should be noted that the implementation of a number of reforms by the government on the popularization of physical education and sports serves the development of the industry and the health of residents. In particular, the protection of education and health of students and young people by state laws ensures a bright future for future professionals. Because of this, it will be necessary for all students and young people to use the privileges given to them in the way of the goal, to ensure physical maturity, no matter where they receive their education. As a result, life experience and practice are the basis for leaving to the future the fact that physical education has raised the social and historical essences and is a high factor in human life as much as possible. In particular, the development of a special state program serves the physical and spiritual growth of young people, their development into well-rounded people with the most modern intellectual knowledge.

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